

Evaluation of the reproducibility and crystal tracking precision of TEM goniometers in tomography experiments

Marco Santucci, Ute Kolb*

Johannes Gutenberg University Mainz Mainz, Germany

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ABSTRACT

Nanocrystalline materials are the basis of many novel engineered systems, including batteries, nanocomposites, and glass ceramics. Three-dimensional electron diffraction (3D ED) has become a key technique for structural analysis of such materials, offering clear advantages over conventional X-ray diffraction. Commercial routine 3D ED acquisition allowing for measurements of crystals down to ~ 750 nm is now standard, but pushing the measurable size towards a few tens of nanometers introduces new challenges, requiring robust crystal-tracking methods. At this scale, TEM automation, reliable object detection, and high mechanical precision of the goniometer are essential.

PyFast-ADT is introduced as a modular automation framework for 3D ED data collection, extending the measurable size range through improved crystal tracking routines. Its Python architecture enhances shareability and promotes facility automation within the 3D ED and Cryo-EM communities. The PatchworkCC algorithm combines Cross-Correlation with Kalman Filtering to achieve fully automatic crystal tracking with improved accuracy and minimal user supervision. Characterization of goniometer reproducibility revealed a rapid decrease behaviour degrading precision, addressed by the HiPerGonio procedure, which stabilizes performance and supports optimal TEM/sample holder choices.

Together, these developments enable fully automated 3D ED data collection on 25 nm nanocrystals embedded in a glass-ceramic matrix, increasing throughput up to sixfold and advancing reproducible, high-throughput structure determination at the nanometer scale.

1. Introduction

Three-dimensional electron diffraction (3D ED) has emerged as a powerful technique for studying micro- and nano-sized crystals, enabling structural analysis where X-ray diffraction is limited [1–4]. Its main advantage is the ability to investigate crystals 2–3 orders of magnitude smaller than those used in X-ray methods, making it indispensable for quantum dots, battery materials, glass ceramics, and biomedical nanocomposites [5–8]. However, reducing the illuminated area amplifies problems related to goniometer alignment, making crystal tracking essential to collect useful data.

Despite its potential, 3D ED faces important challenges. Dynamical diffraction, generally reduced due to the recording of off-zone diffraction patterns, is still present, complicating data interpretation, and geometric constraints in Transmission Electron Microscopes (TEMs) limit reciprocal space coverage from a single dataset. In practice, very small nanocrystals data collection is often performed semi-automatically

or manually due to limited software automation and suboptimal hardware performance. Manual acquisition is both time-consuming (up to 1–2 hours per dataset) and prone to error, particularly for inexperienced users. Software automation has thus become crucial to smooth experiments, reduce acquisition time, and increase the chances of obtaining datasets suitable for structure solution and crystal structure refinement. Several non-commercial solutions are used to collect 3D ED data, such as Instamatic (SU) [9], Fast-ADT (JGU) [10], MicroED (UCLA) [11], RATS (FZU) [12], SerialEM (CU) [13], and Legimon (NY) [14]. However, most of these primarily handle automated tilt acquisition of diffraction patterns, while only a few implement robust crystal tracking routines specifically designed for 3D ED.

Diffraction patterns are generally acquired using Selected Area Electron Diffraction (SAED) or Nano-Beam Electron Diffraction (NBED) methods. While SAED illuminates the full sample, selecting the area of interest with the selected area aperture, NBED defines the diffraction area by using a smaller beam diameter with the aid of a small C2 aperture, allowing for a reduced total electron fluence. Crystal tracking

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: kolb@uni-mainz.de (U. Kolb).

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Glossary

3D ED	3-Dimensional Electron Diffraction
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscope
STEM	Scanning TEM
NBED	Nano Beam Electron Diffraction
HiPerGonio	High Performance Goniometer
ADT	Automated Diffraction Tomography
PEDT	Precession Electron Diffraction Tomography
cRED	continuous Rotation Electron Diffraction
CC	Cross Correlation
KF	Kalman Filter
ROI	Region of Interest
GUI	Graphical User Interface
FEG	Field Emission Gun
CA	Condenser Aperture
HAADF	High-Angle Annular Dark Field
CL	Camera Length
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
fps	frames per second

becomes particularly valuable in the context of NBED, where the probe size is tuned to match crystalline domains as small as a few tens of nanometers. In such cases, keeping the crystal under the electron beam during the whole tilt series is critical. Standard TEM goniometers typically exhibit crystal shift above 500 nanometers during a tomography experiment, making tracking essential for reliable data acquisition on crystals below 500 nm size. This motivates the development of improved algorithms and procedures that enhance precision and reduce crystal shift, as well as the need for manual procedures.

1.1. State of the art in 3D ED crystal tracking

Currently, two main 3D ED acquisition protocols are used Automated Diffraction Tomography (ADT) and Continuous Rotation Electron Diffraction (cRED)

In ADT, the goniometer drives iteratively to a list of specific alpha tilt angles. At each angle the goniometer is held steady, and a diffraction pattern is acquired, while the electron beam is precessed to integrate the reciprocal space at a fixed precession angle. The ADT method provides accurate angles, good intensity information at the cost of longer acquisition times due to its iterative nature. Moreover, this acquisition mode is often the chosen one when no automation is available, and in the case of manual acquisition, but it requires a precession hardware unit in most cases.

In cRED, the goniometer drives at a defined speed in a continuous way from the starting to the final angle of the dataset. The goniometer speed is a fixed parameter obtained from the ratio between angular alpha tilt step and exposure time. A diffraction pattern is collected, each frame constituting an integration of a certain wedge of the reciprocal space over its exposure time, during the stage movement in a movie-like way. This method is often fast and efficient for larger crystals or beam-sensitive samples. Nevertheless, a minimum degree of automation is usually required to synchronize goniometer and detector actions, and it is suggested to use a relatively fast detector, at least capable of recording 1 FPS, and with a very short readout time.

In both cases, the introduction of crystal tracking is possible and has been a major step forward for reducing the measurable crystal sizes from micrometers to nanometers. Tracking allows the electron probe (or the stage) to follow the crystal during tilting, reducing the necessary probe size and thereby minimizing background noise and increasing the

chances of collecting single crystal data. Nowadays, two available modes of tracking exist, called *pre-calibration* and *in-situ* crystal tracking methods.

In *pre-calibration* tracking, a pre-experiment is carried out to map the crystal movement of a chosen target across the whole tilt range. Thanks to an object detection method (often Cross Correlation), a tracking file is generated, recording the xy coordinates of the target at specific tilt angles. During the following 3D ED experiment, the electron beam is shifted according to this file, under the assumption that the goniometer will reproduce the same path. This assumption is the limiting factor of the technique, directly limiting the electron probe size [10]. This strategy, first implemented in Fast-ADT, is most effective in STEM imaging mode combined with ADT. The *pre-calibration* method allows the use of significantly smaller probes (e.g. 200 nm), improving signal-to-noise by reducing contributions from the carbon support, and it preserves reciprocal space completeness, at the cost of an increased electron fluence and sensitivity to the reproducibility of the goniometer motion.

In an *in-situ* tracking method, no pre-experiment is required. Instead, directly during the 3D ED acquisition, the acquisition process is periodically paused (e.g. 5 degrees) and the diffraction pattern is defocused to produce an image of the target crystal. An object detection algorithm finds the xy position and re-centers the crystal under the beam by applying a corrective shift by electron-beam or stage shift. The acquisition then resumes by refocusing until the next checkpoint. This method, originally developed in Instamatic, works particularly well in TEM mode and with cRED. It is fast and convenient, as it requires no pre-experiment and is not affected by the goniometer reproducibility. However, the electron probe should be sufficiently large and intense to ensure reliable recognition of the target during the defocusing process. The probe size is mainly limited by the tomographic stage alignment made by expert engineers and instabilities or non-reproducible jumps during the tilting, because the target tracked crystal must be visible during each correction step. In the case of cRED acquisition, the periodic interruptions to track the crystal introduce extra missing wedges in the 3D reciprocal space, if the stage is not stopped, while in ADT acquisition, no extra wedges are generated.

While both strategies have proven valuable, they come with inherent limitations, especially mechanical, that are particularly critical for very small nanocrystals.

Pre-calibration tracking enables the smallest probe sizes possible, but object detection methods should be robust and precise enough to guarantee correct tracking paths in a fully automated way, even for small and agglomerated particles.

In-situ tracking is affected by the overall shift of the target during the whole tilt series, limiting the probe size. If the probe size matches the crystal size, the object detection could easily fail the task due to partial visibility or false positives, and the tracking step needs to be iterated frequently to compensate for it. When this condition occurs, extra missing wedges are introduced, and instabilities in goniometer velocity become more critical.

Recently, a new standalone method is in development based on 4D-STEM like approach that is worth mentioning [15,16]. This technique requires the collection of a tomographic 4D-STEM dataset, using a small electron probe raster scanned on a target area, in ADT or cRED approach. From the resulting tomographic 4D-STEM dataset, tracking images at each tilt step can be reconstructed by an algorithm, and the target 3D ED dataset extracted using a crystal tracking file approach, like in a *pre-calibration* crystal tracking experiment, without collecting two successive tilt scans. This could potentially bypass the intrinsic needs of goniometer reproducibility of the *pre-calibration* method at the cost of a high degree of automation required, and drastically increasing the dataset size from 300 MBs up to a few TBs. It's worth mentioning that not only one 3D ED dataset is obtained, but potentially a bunch of them could be obtained in a single acquisition using this approach.

The choice between the two "traditional" methods is often highly

sample-, setup-, and degree of automation dependent. Especially for nanocrystals only a few tens of nanometers in size, neither approach guarantees fully reliable automation. Our strategies and efforts are mainly devoted to improve the *pre-calibration* crystal tracking method combined with ADT. To reach our goal, understanding of the mechanical performances of each microscope/holder pair is necessary, together with an improved object detection algorithm, specifically designed for tomographic experiments.

1.2. Applications

This work presents a set of methodological advances implemented in the redesigned PyFast-ADT software package. These include a new object-detection algorithm robust to false positives for 3D ED crystal tracking (PatchworkCC), and dedicated routines to characterize and improve goniometer precision and reproducibility in successive tracking experiments for standard TEMs through the HiPerGonio (High Performance Goniometer) procedure. Together, these developments enable fully automated 3D ED acquisition even for challenging nanocrystalline samples, eliminating the need for manual acquisition.

A recently discovered new phase of LaPO_4 embedded in a complex glass ceramic matrix is selected as a case study to show that fully automated 3D ED data acquisition is doable even for nanocrystalline materials using an electron probe of 25 nm size to match the crystal size, drastically reducing experimental time and user expertise. The implemented improvements enable the investigation of challenging materials, which is complicated with every other crystallographic technique, leading 3D ED to the state-of-the-art technique for the investigation of low-dimensional materials below 100 nm up to a few tens of nanometers.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Py-Fast ADT – data acquisition software

PyFast-ADT is developed in Python3, improving accessibility for the community and simplifying the implementation of new features thanks to its modular design. PyFast-ADT source code is available under the GPLv3 licence. Resources and documentation are available respectively on GitHub and ReadTheDocs.

The software is implemented and tested on FEI Tecnai F30 and Tecnai Spirit (EMCM/JGU@Mainz), mounting respectively an ASI Timepix1 and a Gatan US4000 Detectors for the F30 and a TVIPS XF416r GPU accelerated and a Gatan US2000 Detectors for the SPIRIT. The JEOL implementation is tested on a JEM 2100F (TU Darmstadt), mounting a QD Merlin Detector. The software is installed and tested for the new generation ThermoFisher Krios equipped with a Ceta16 Detector (MPIP@Mainz) to collect 3D ED data. PyFast-ADT can track crystals in both TEM and Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM) mode and acquire data using a stepwise or continuous goniometer movement, usually referred to as ADT (sometimes also referred to as Precession assisted Electron Diffraction Tomography - PEDT) and cRED acquisition mode. Additional tools are implemented in the software, such as tracking precision for goniometers reproducibility evaluation, which is a critical parameter for a *pre-calibration* crystal tracking procedure, and a hand panel simulator, relevant for remote usage of the software.

2.2. PatchworkCC – crystal tracking algorithm

PyFast-ADT implements a new algorithm for crystal tracking optimized for low-dimensional crystallites called PatchworkCC. This improves the reliability of Cross-Correlation (CC) in a tomography pre-experiment by reducing false positives. The algorithm uses the predicted positions from a Kalman Filter (KF) to detect false positives in the CC calculation that tend to spoil the automatic crystal tracking routine,

requiring manual correction from the user. Thanks to the KF, the algorithm can discriminate between the top 10 results of the cross-correlation of the target Region Of Interest (ROI) and return the closest resulting position predicted by KF. The PatchworkCC algorithm is used in this article for both the tracking precision characterization and the 3D ED data collection, combined with *pre-calibration* crystal tracking without manual interaction of the user. Anyway, in case of failure of the automatic procedure, the user can recalculate the tracking positions by changing the ROI without re-acquiring the pre-experiment images, or manually select the crystal positions from the Graphical User Interface (GUI) in an interactive way, by manually clicking the incorrect crystal tracking positions directly on the acquired images.

2.3. Microscope setups and sample preparation

The tracking precision data presented in this manuscript are acquired using an FEI Tecnai F30 S-TWIN TEM equipped with a Schottky-type Field Emission Gun (FEG) operating at 300 kV and an FEI Tecnai Spirit TEM equipped with a LaB_6 gun operating at 120 kV. The F30 is running in STEM mode and the Spirit in TEM mode, both using a Condenser Aperture (CA) of 10 μm and in microprobe mode. These microscopes are respectively equipped with a Fischione High-Angle Annular Dark-Field (HAADF) detector and a TVIPS XF416R CMOS detector for the collection of crystal tracking images. BaSO_4 is used as a standard material for the PatchworkCC, crystal tracking precision development, and testing [17]. The material is finely ground, dispersed in EtOH, and drop-cast onto a continuous carbon-coated side of a standard TEM copper grid (200 mesh).

2.4. Tracking precision – evaluation routine

Tracking precision is evaluated by repeatedly following the same object in a series of tomographic pre-experiments for a certain microscope/holder pair. Both electron microscopes are tested using an FEI single tilt tomography holder and a Simple Origin cryo-tomography holder. The two holders are chosen for their different designs and functions. The FEI single tilt tomography holder is about 4.5 times lighter with respect to the Simple Origin cryo-tomography holder due to the absence of the liquid nitrogen reservoir. Moreover, the weight is distributed homogeneously in the single tilt tomography holder, which results in a central center of mass, whereas in the cryo-tomography holder, the presence of the liquid nitrogen reservoir shifts the center of mass towards the side. Respectively, the two holders weigh 136 g (single tilt tomography holder) and 634 g (cryo-tomography holder).

At the beginning of each experiment, at 0° α tilt, a single xyz backlash correction is performed following the procedure described by Liu et al [18]. The goniometer is then tilted to the starting angle, and the pre-experiment is initiated by applying a 3° α backlash correction. Images of the object are collected every 5° across the selected tilt range.

This data collection is repeated five more times, yielding a total of six consecutive tomographic pre-experiment datasets for the same target object. Using PatchworkCC, each tracking path is automatically constructed from an initially defined ROI of the object in the first pre-experiment. The paths are made relative by subtracting the initial xy coordinates of the target in each pre-experiment. Displacement curves are then calculated by comparing consecutive paths (run 1 = 1st vs. 2nd, run 2 = 2nd vs. 3rd, ... run 5 = 5th vs. 6th).

From each displacement curve, only the maximum displacement value is extracted, providing a single scalar measurement for that run. This procedure, hereafter referred to as “standard” acquisition protocol, results in a time series of maximum displacements across the six paths collected. The entire experiment is repeated three times, and the values corresponding to the same run number are averaged to obtain the mean displacement and standard deviation and plotted as average displacement vs run #. This protocol is applied at different goniometer rotation speeds (40, 22, 10, and $2^\circ/\text{s}$) to identify the optimal stage speed for

stepwise tracking experiments and to evaluate an average displacement value as a function of the speed chosen, which is possible to be calculated by averaging together the results of each run #.

To address the stage instability often observed in the first runs of the time series, an additional step called HiPerGonio can be added in each pre-experiment after each alpha backlash correction.

In HiPerGonio variants, the first n runs are treated as dummy cycles. Data collection begins from the $(n+1)$ run of the time-series, where the system has already stabilized and reproducibility is improved. For example, with HiPerGonio $n = 1$, one continuous rotation back and forth from start to end is performed to skip the first datapoint; with $n = 2$, two runs are skipped before starting data collection. This procedure ensures that the reported displacement values reflect only the stable behaviour of the goniometer, improving the reproducibility of a *pre-calibration* crystal tracking experiment.

2.5. Average tracking displacement of PatchworkCC and manual picking methods

Average tracking displacement data from PatchworkCC and manual picking methods are evaluated following the same object in three successive tomographic pre-experiments following a similar procedure as tracking precision method. For the PatchworkCC method, each tracking path is automatically constructed from an initially defined ROI of the object in the first pre-experiment. Instead for manual picking, each tracking path is constructed from the user by clicking iteratively on the target position in each frame of the tomography experiment. The paths are made relative by subtracting the initial xy coordinates of the target in each pre-experiment. Displacement curves are then calculated by comparing consecutive paths (run 1 = 1st vs. 2nd, run 2 = 2nd vs. 3rd). From each displacement curve, only the maximum displacement value is extracted. The same three consecutive tomographic pre-experiment datasets are re-evaluated, two additional times, from the object detection step. The resulting nine maximum displacement values are averaged to obtain the mean displacement and standard deviations. The pixelsize used for conversion from nm to pixels is 4.4 nm/pixels.

2.6. 3D ED data collection

The LaPO₄ nanocrystals investigated are embedded in a glass-ceramic sample (labeled as X3-3) from a previous work of Gollé-Leidreiter et al. [19]. The glass is mainly composed of an amorphous silica matrix embedding nano-crystallites such as ZrTiO₄, spinel and LaPO₄ that have an anisotropic wormy-like form and the grains, of sizes about 60 and 20 nm, respectively, in the longer and shorter directions. These crystals tend to grow interlocked, making it more challenging to acquire single crystal data. The glass sample is mounted on a 100 mesh Cu TEM grid using an epoxy resin and ion-milled using a Gatan DuoMill 600 to ensure the transmission of the electron probe.

The LaPO₄ 3D ED data are acquired using the FEI Tecnai F30 S-TWIN TEM at 300 kV. All data are acquired with a CA of 10 μ m in STEM microprobe mode, using gun lens 8 and spot size 6, with a quasi-parallel electron probe size of 25 nm in diameter. NBED patterns are collected by an ASI Timepix1 detector (512 \times 512 pixels) at 300 mm Camera Length (CL) and exposure time of 0.5 s. STEM images of the samples are acquired using an HAADF detector at the same CL. The data collection is automatically performed by the python restyled software PyFast-ADT. The software controls all the 3D ED procedure for data collection, synchronizing the TEM and detector components, and storing the final data. Moreover, PyFast-ADT is also able to perform *pre-calibration* crystal tracking, enabling the possibility to work with such a small electron probe and nanocrystalline materials.

NBED patterns from LaPO₄ are collected with both sequential and continuous methods. In the sequential method, diffraction patterns are acquired in 1° tilt steps within the maximum allowed by the sample tilt range and integrated by a precession movement of the electron probe

(ADT) [2,3] with a precession angle of 1°, employing a DigiSTAR unit from NanoMEGAS SPRL. This approach, called Automated Diffraction Tomography (ADT) is described by Mugnaioli et al. [17] and routinely used in our lab. In the continuous method, a certain goniometer speed (deg/s) is calculated by the ratio between user-defined tilt step and exposure time. This speed is then used to rotate the goniometer alpha tilt continuously across the user-defined angular range, and NBED patterns are collected continuously in a movie-like fashion. This approach is known as continuous Rotation Electron Diffraction (cRED) [20–23].

The eADT software was used for 3D ED data processing, such as reconstruction of the 3D volume, and determination of the space group [24]. The reflection file for crystal structure determination and refinement was prepared using the software PETS2.0 [25]. Ab initio structure solution and difference Fourier maps calculation were performed in kinematic approximation ($I \approx |F_{hkl}|^2$) using direct methods implemented in Sir2014 software [26]. The solved crystal structure was kinematically refined using Jana2020, and dynamically refined if possible [27–29].

2.7. Scattered / transmitted beam intensity ratio versus frame number plot

3D ED diffraction patterns are analyzed using a custom Python script to quantify the relative intensity of the central (I_{000}) beam with respect to the rest of the scattered signal (I), without background subtraction or normalization. The central beam is determined from the first diffraction frame, by fitting a one-dimensional Gaussian function, in horizontal and vertical directions independently, with respect to the frame coordinates, to evaluate the full width at half maximum (FWHM) in both directions, and the (000) beam center. The radius of the central beam is defined as the mean value between the half of the mean FWHM along the two axes, plus an additional constant margin of 20 pixels. Using this radius, a circular mask centered on the (000) beam center is generated to separate two regions of the diffraction pattern. The integrated (000) beam intensity (I_{000}) is obtained by summing all pixel intensities within this mask. The scattered intensity (I) is calculated by summing the intensities of all pixels outside the central-beam mask. For each diffraction pattern in the 3D ED dataset, the ratio I/I_{000} is calculated and plotted as a function of frame number.

3. Results

3.1. PyFast-ADT

PyFast-ADT has been developed as a fully refactored and extended platform for automated 3D ED data acquisition. It is based on the original Fast-ADT, developed by Plana Ruiz et al. by removing legacy dependencies, broadening instrument compatibility, and introducing a modular software architecture that accelerates development and makes easier shareability for custom EM facilities [10].

PyFast-ADT is implemented in Python3 to overcome limitations inherent to DigitalMicrograph® scripting, such as the need for a DigiScan unit for STEM operation and the constraint of using only Gatan cameras. Moreover, python is widely adopted in the scientific community and empowered by many open-source packages for computer vision, image processing, and Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning (AI/ML) tools, which in the future could extend the capabilities of the program. The use of python lowers the barrier for new contributors while making the system easier to maintain and grow in the long term.

The software architecture is reorganized into two encapsulated layers sketched in Fig. 1. The abstracted layer (green dashed rectangle) defines hardware-agnostic interfaces for all functions required to run a tomography experiment (e.g., stage control, detector readout, synchronization, tracking, and logging). Methods in this layer are expressed at a high level and do not depend on any specific microscope or camera Application Programming Interface (API).

Fig. 1. PyFast-ADT architecture. A hardware-agnostic abstracted layer (green area) exposes the interfaces for 3D ED workflows, while hardware-specific adaptors (orange area) translate vendor APIs for microscopes and detectors. The orange area can be freely expanded by adding new adaptors to interface new APIs.

The hardware-specific layer (orange dashed rectangle) translates the vendor APIs (microscope and detector) into the respective abstracted layer components. Each adaptor inherits from a well-defined base class, ensuring that all mandatory methods are implemented consistently and if necessary, enabling the support for new hardware without rewriting core logic from scratch.

This architecture encapsulation allows new features to be implemented once, within the abstracted layer, and become immediately available across all supported configurations.

By decoupling from DigitalMicrograph® and Digiscan needs, PyFast-ADT improves the shareability within the 3D ED community. Now, the software can directly control TEM platforms (e.g., FEI/ThermoFisher and JEOL) and operate with multiple detector brands commonly used in the 3D ED field (e.g. Gatan, TVIPS, ASI, and QD). This enables both TEM and STEM operation across stepwise and continuous acquisition modes for every kind of available custom setup.

Development and validation have been performed on an FEI Tecnai F30 and a Tecnai Spirit equipped with Gatan US4000/US2000, ASI Timepix1, and TVIPS XF416R (GPU-accelerated) cameras. Additional support has been implemented for a ThermoFisher Krios with a CETA 16M camera, and a JEOL JEM-2100F with a QD Merlin camera.

The object-oriented design through adaptor strategy provides extensibility to new microscope and detector brands by implementing only the missing adaptor(s). Moreover, all the core features (e.g., acquisition routine, tracking algorithms, and characterization tools) reside in a single code path, simplifying upgrades, bug fixes, and maintainability of the program.

PyFast-ADT source code is maintained in GitHub to maximize transparency, reproducibility, and collaborative development of new adaptors and improvement of the core algorithms. This fundamental step forward is important to enable the community-driven evolution of 3D ED automation and acquisition tools.

About 3D ED data acquisition, PyFast-ADT supports both stepwise and continuous acquisition modes for 3D ED data collection, which are used to perform ADT and cRED data acquisition strategies, respectively. Synchronization between the microscope and the detector is fully handled by the program. In both modes, the user can apply, on top of the

basic acquisition mode, if needed, a crystal-tracking routine, stage backlash correction method, and variable goniometer speeds, improving flexibility depending on the material challenges.

Regarding crystal tracking and especially tracking precision, PyFast-ADT includes new tools to characterize the microscope/holder pair reproducibility and precision. These routines are of great help to understand the mechanical capabilities and the optimum acquisition parameters (e.g., rotation speed, exposure time, step size) of your facility. For the sake of crystal tracking routine development, PyFast-ADT can evaluate the crystal tracking performances of different object detection algorithms both online and offline, allowing for optimizing and testing new algorithms easily. All the tracking precision data shown in this manuscript are generated by these PyFast-ADT tools.

3.2. PatchworkCC a robust detection method for automated crystal tracking

During the generation of a *pre-calibration* crystal tracking file, images of the target crystal are collected to generate a list of angles (deg), x (pix), y (pix), that will be used as tracking positions in the 3D ED data collection. There are mainly three sources of errors in a *pre-calibration* crystal tracking experiment that could cause a data collection to fail. First, the object detection method needs to find the correct position of the target object in the tracking images. As a result, a continuous crystal tracking path is expected accordingly to the rigid body rotation model [30–32]. Second, the *pre-calibration* method is based on the reproducibility between two successive tomography experiments is good enough [10] Third, the e-beam shift or stage shift is precise enough to recentre the e-beam or the crystal. In this manuscript, we demonstrate the effect of the first two sources of error and if necessary, how they can be tackled to maximize the success of a 3D ED data collection, especially in the case of very small nanocrystals around 25 nm size.

In object detection, a true positive is scored when the result of the detection method coincides with your target particle to track. Instead, a false positive occurs when the object detection result differs from your target to track, resulting in an incorrect xy position that usually requires manual correction from the user to be solved. This problem occurs often

in electron microscopy because multiple crystals at the nanoscale can have similar shapes or features, and the CC is not able to discriminate properly between them, just by image similarity. During tomography, the problem becomes even worse, due to alpha tilting, because shape and contrast changes occur, resulting in additional confusion.

PyFast-ADT introduces a new fully automated crystal tracking routine, replacing the semi-supervised approach of the previous implementation. The method is based on the newly developed PatchworkCC algorithm, which combines CC with Kalman filtering (KF) to overcome false positive results, achieving reliable crystal tracking positions, based on image similarity and motion prediction of the object to track, even under challenging experimental conditions.

The Kalman filter is a recursive state estimation algorithm that combines a predictive motion model with experimental measurements to estimate the state (position and velocity) of a dynamical system over time [33–35]. This property makes the Kalman filter particularly suitable for object tracking, where temporal correlations between successive frames can be exploited [36–39]. Its effectiveness comes from continuously refining the state estimate by combining the current prediction with incoming measurements. The Kalman filter works through three fundamental steps: initialization, prediction, and update.

During initialization, the state vector is defined to contain the variables of the linear motion model, describing the object to be tracked. The state vector is defined as

$$\mathbf{x} = [x, y, v_x, v_y]^T$$

where x, y are the object coordinates, and v_x, v_y are the velocity components.

A linear constant velocity 2D motion model is assumed and encoded in the state transition matrix A , defined as

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \Delta t & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & \Delta t \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\Delta t = 0.1$ s

The measurement vector is initialized to store the object position obtained from CC, which is necessary to introduce new data into the update step. The measurement vector (z) is defined below, together with the measurement matrix (H), as

$$\mathbf{z} = [x_{CC}, y_{CC}]^T, H = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Several covariance matrices are also initialized. The state covariance matrix P is initialized as a diagonal matrix, with large uncertainties, such as

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The measurement noise covariance matrix is defined as

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{x, meas}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_{y, meas}^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\sigma_{x,y, meas} = 0.01$. Small measurement variances are chosen to reflect high confidence in the experimental measurements.

The process noise covariance matrix Q is defined using a discrete white noise model [40,41].

$$Q = \sigma^2 \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\Delta t^4}{4} & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta t^4}{4} & 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} \\ \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & 0 & \Delta t^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta t^3}{2} & 0 & \Delta t^2 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\sigma = 0.1$.

In PatchworkCC, the first tracking frame is used to determine the initial object position (x_i, y_i), from a user-defined region of interest (ROI). The initial state vector is initialized as

$$\mathbf{x} = [x_i, y_i, 0, 0]^T$$

At this stage, the velocity components are initialized with zeros and assigned large uncertainties, since they cannot be known from a single measurement.

After initialization, the filter enters in the prediction-update cycle. During the prediction step, the state vector (x_{k-1}) is propagated forward in time using the motion model in A , yielding the prior state estimate (x_k^-), and the prior state covariance (P_k^-).

$$\mathbf{x}_k^- = A\mathbf{x}_{k-1}$$

$$P_k^- = AP_{k-1}A^T + Q$$

In the update step, the Kalman gain (K_k) is evaluated based on the prior state covariance (P_k^-), and the measurement noise covariance (R). K_k is evaluated as the optimal weighting factor that minimizes the mean squared error (MSE) of the posterior estimate (x_k), by balancing the contributions of the measurement (z_k) and the prior (x_k^-), yielding to the best estimate of the state.

$$K_k = P_k^- H^T (H P_k^- H^T + R)^{-1}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{x}_k^- + K_k(z_k - H\mathbf{x}_k^-)$$

$$P_k = (I - K_k H)P_k^-$$

where I is the identity matrix.

During the first prediction-update cycle, the filter predicts the prior with a large covariance, due to initialization. The filter behaves conservatively, returning the initial position as the first predicted position. PatchworkCC identifies the top 10 maxima in the CC map, by iteratively evaluating the CC result, saving the found position, and covering it by a black mask of the ROI size (Fig. 2b PatchworkCC map). Among these candidates, the CC maximum closest to the Kalman filter prediction is provided to the update step, as the measurement (z_k). During the update step, the KF generates the posterior, combining the measurement and the predicted position, allowing the velocity to evolve from zero toward a velocity consistent with the observed motion.

As tracking proceeds, in each iteration, a new measurement is introduced in the prediction-update cycle, allowing to refine both the state estimate, and its covariance. Consequently, the accuracy of the predicted state tends to improve along the tracking path, due to a better estimation of the object velocity, up to reaching convergency. Overall, while CC alone identifies candidate object positions based only on image similarity, the KF assures motion consistency by selecting the candidate that are compatible with the predicted motion of the object.

The PatchworkCC algorithm workflow is reported in Fig. 2c. In Fig. 2a, PatchworkCC produced an accurate crystal tracking path where CC method failed or required manual correction.

Moreover, PatchworkCC, compared to manual position picking, results in a tracking path less noisy and more accurate. This becomes relevant for very small nanocrystals where the displacement between

Fig. 2. Comparison between PatchworkCC (blue) and CC (red) crystal tracking path (a). The scalebar reported is $1 \mu\text{m}$. Resulting CC map views generated using a user-defined ROI from the perspective of CC and PatchworkCC (b). PatchworkCC algorithm workflow (c).

two tracking paths needs to be reduced to a minimum.

In Fig. 3a, two crystal tracking paths, extracted from the first run of a tracking precision experiment, obtained from PatchworkCC (blue) and manual picking (yellow) are displayed. The manual picking curve shows a noisier path with respect to the PatchworkCC one. This is expected considering the size of the image, which is a typical $1024 \times 1024 \text{ pixel}^2$ STEM image from an HAADF detector. In this case, the user produces a larger uncertainty in the tracking position (manual picking) with respect to an object detection algorithm (PatchworkCC). The first tracking displacement curves are reported in Fig. 3b, for each method. The manual picking (yellow) method shows displacements up to 46 nm, with respect to PatchworkCC (blue) method, which shows displacements up to 18 nm. The tracking precision is calculated three times, within the same successive tomographic datasets. The maximum tracking displacement results are averaged, and displayed in Fig. 3c, showing 3

times better performances of the PatchworkCC with respect to manual picking.

3.3. Characterization of Tracking Precision dependence on goniometer speed

Assessing the reproducibility of stage movement in tomography experiments is challenging. In practice, reproducibility is often poor, which makes it difficult to extract meaningful precision data for microscope/holder pairs. This limitation directly constrains the smallest measurable crystal size and affects the likelihood of successfully collecting single-crystal 3D ED data, as reported by Plana-Ruiz et al. [10]. For this reason, it is essential to characterize tracking precision for each microscope/holder pair.

A series of consecutive crystal tracking paths are collected on the

Fig. 3. STEM image of the selected crystal and crystal tracking path. The scalebar reported is $1 \mu\text{m}$. The inset shows a magnified view of the tracked target, marked by a red cross. Crystal tracking path plots from CC (red), PatchworkCC (blue), and manual picking (yellow) (a). First tracking displacement curves of PatchworkCC (blue) and manual picking (yellow) methods as a function of the tilt angle (b). Average tracking displacement of PatchworkCC and manual picking methods in pixels (c).

same target. Successive pairs of paths are compared, yielding a time series of maximum displacement values, labelled as runs. Ideally, all runs should yield comparable displacement values, reflecting consistent goniometer behaviour. Instead, some microscope/holder pairs exhibit a rapid decrease of the displacement, with the displacement being large initially, and then decreasing, quickly reaching a plateau (Fig. 4a). This behaviour is problematic because the studied system should perform consistently from the first run onward. Averaging such displacement data, therefore, produces unrealistic standard deviations (Fig. 4c).

To address this lack of reproducibility, we developed the HiPerGonio procedure, implemented in PyFast-ADT. The concept is to skip the first n runs (where the rapid decrease occurs) and start the data collection once the plateau is reached. This is possible by performing a dummy tilt cycle using the alpha tilt axis, emulating the acquisition of a tomography experiment. For example, with HiPerGonio $n = 1$, an initial dummy tilt cycle is performed before data collection, effectively discarding the unstable first tracking path. If $n > 1$, multiple cycles are executed before acquisition begins, skipping to the $(n+1)$ tracking path of the time series.

The effect is illustrated in Fig. 4. With standard acquisition (Fig. 4a and c), reproducibility improves quickly over successive runs due to the rapid decrease behaviour explained before. With HiPerGonio applied (Fig. 4b and d), reproducibility is achieved immediately, resulting in meaningful average displacement and standard deviation values that can be used to characterize microscope/holder performance. Importantly, this effect is not universal: some microscope/holder combinations show it strongly, while others do not. Therefore, we recommend characterizing tracking precision in at least five successive runs for each microscope/holder pair to understand if HiPerGonio is required.

If the data resemble Fig. 4a, applying HiPerGonio ($n \geq 1$) is strongly recommended, as it substantially improves reproducibility. If the data resemble Fig. 4b, HiPerGonio offers no additional benefit and can be skipped to save time. As an additional example, Fig. 1SI reports the same analysis for the Tecnai Spirit tomography holder pair, where HiPerGonio

($n = 2$) was required to achieve optimal reproducibility.

Fig. 4 d further shows that both average displacement and standard deviation are influenced by stage speed. While no simple trend is observed, operating at the maximum stage speed (40 deg/s, which is the default in FEL/TFS microscopes) is generally not recommended when high precision is required.

3.4. Tracking precision comparison between Tecnai F30 and Tecnai Spirit with FEI single tilt tomography holder

Now that reproducibility is assured, it is possible to compare different microscopes using the same holder, ensuring the comparability by applying HiPerGonio where necessary. Two TEMs tracking precision is studied using two different types of holders, a tomography holder and a cryo-tomography holder, respectively.

In Fig. 5, the tracking precision comparison between the 2 investigated TEMs using the tomography holder is shown. On average, the data shows that the Tecnai Spirit achieves better precision at all speeds with respect to the Tecnai F30. Moreover, the 40 deg/s stage speed is the worst in both experiments in terms of average displacement and standard deviations. To reduce experimental time in a crystal tracking experiment of a very small nanocrystal, the optimum speed to use is 10 deg/s, where the Tecnai F30 achieves 21 ± 11 nm and the Tecnai Spirit achieves 11 ± 4 nm if HiPerGonio ($n=2$) is used.

3.5. Tracking precision comparison between Tecnai F30 and Tecnai Spirit with Simple Origin cryo-tomography holder

In Fig. 6, the tracking precision comparison between the 2 investigated TEMs using the cryo-tomography holder is shown. On average, the data shows that the Tecnai Spirit achieves better precision at all speeds, and the maximum stage speed results in the worst speed to use in terms of precision. In general, the optimum speed to use this holder is 22 deg/

Fig. 4. Tracking precision, stage speed 10 deg/s, standard and HiPerGonio acquisition, respectively (a, b). Maximum average displacement as a function of the stage speed used, standard (c) and HiPerGonio (d) acquisition, respectively. Stage speed 10 deg/s is marked by an asterisk. The data were collected in the Tecnai F30, cryo-tomography holder.

Fig. 5. Tracking precision comparison as a function of the stage speed in two different TEMs. The data were collected in the microscope Tecnai F30 (a) and Tecnai Spirit (b) using the tomography holder.

Fig. 6. Tracking precision comparison as a function of the stage speed in two different TEMs. The data were collected in the microscope Tecnai F30 (a) and Tecnai Spirit (b) using the cryo-tomography holder.

s. In this condition, the Tecnai F30 achieves a precision around 71 ± 37 nm using HiPerGonio ($n = 1$), which sets the limit for the electron beam size to use. For the Tecnai Spirit, at the suggested speed, 32 ± 12 nm precision, without the need of HiPerGonio is achieved using this holder.

The Tecnai F30 with this holder achieves really high displacement values. These performances drastically reduce the chances of measuring a single crystal 3D ED dataset using crystal tracking, from very small nanocrystal, around 25 nm size.

In Table 1SI, it is reported a resume of the tracking precision performances of each microscope/holder pair studied, using speed 10 deg/s. In the presented tracking precision experiments, PatchworkCC automatically detected 419/420 crystal tracking paths correctly, while just one experimental path required manual correction, achieving a success rate of 99.76%.

3.6. Fully automated 3D ED ADT data acquisition from very small nanocrystals

Thanks to the above-mentioned optimization, fully automated 3D ED data acquisition using an electron beam size of 25 nm is doable, and examples are reported below.

The material investigated is a recently discovered crystalline phase of LaPO_4 embedded in a glass-ceramic matrix, using manually acquired 3D ED ADT datasets [19]. These very small nanocrystals crystals are challenging to measure single crystal data due to their anisotropic shape, and interlocked grains. An electron probe size of 10 nm, delivered single crystal data suitable for 3D ED structure elucidation, showing few

reflections from adjacent crystals in the 3D reciprocal space. The material is measured in the Tecnai F30, using the FEI single tilt tomography holder, to prove the improved performance of PyFast-ADT, and the new tools developed for automated acquisition of 3D ED ADT from very small nanocrystals.

Due to the S-Twin objective lens geometry, this holder can rotate around the alpha axis about 85 degrees maximum. The aim is to demonstrate that a similar data quality can be achieved in a fully automated way. 7 datasets are collected from glass ceramic sample, where in 4 of them, the unit cell of the target LaPO_4 is found. The best dataset (exp.6) in terms of % non-empty frames, R_{int} , completeness, is reported here. In Table 3 SI is reported the statistics up to structure solution of the collected datasets.

A crystal tracking file using PatchworkCC is generated between -40 and +40 degrees in a stepwise approach, and the obtained path is shown in Fig. 7 a, while in Fig. 2SI, several images collected during the crystal tracking procedure are reported to highlight the false positives and contrast change challenges of the sample for an object detection method. From Fig. 7 a, the CC object detection method results in 17 wrong positions over 81 measured, scattered away from the correct crystal path. Nevertheless, the PatchworkCC algorithm automatically corrects these positions, generating a smoother path with respect to the manual picking ones. In Fig. 7 b, from the 3D ED ADT dataset collected, the scattered / transmitted beam intensity ratio for each frame is evaluated. When the intensity ratio approaches zero, it is a characteristic feature of diffraction patterns where mostly the transmitted beam is present due to a crystal tracking procedure failure. Instead, when a spike up is found, this

Fig. 7. Crystal tracking path of LaPO₄ crystal using different object detection methods (red, blue, and yellow dots are respectively positions from CC, PatchworkCC, and manual picking) calculated from stepwise HAADF images. The scalebar reported is 200 nm (a). Scattered / transmitted beam intensity ratio versus frame number plot. The transmitted (000) beam intensity is computed by summing pixel counts within a circular mask around the 000 beam, while all intensity outside this mask is treated as scattered signal. Their ratio is calculated for each frame and shown as a function of frame number (b). Single crystal ADT individual diffraction patterns collected from LaPO₄. From left to right, these are frame numbers 5, 41 and 71 marked with * in plot b (c).

highlights the presence of a diffraction pattern where many reflections are in diffraction conditions and high scattered intensity is expected, like the presence of a single crystal zone axis diffraction pattern. The plot shows that, from frame 35 up to 81, a progressive increase in the intensity ratio occurs, but nowhere zero intensity ratio is detected. In the SI material, additional 3D ED ADT datasets are present which show that every dataset produces a curve with different overall shape. In Fig. 7 c, three ADT patterns are shown to highlight three different regions of the plot in Fig. 7 b (start, middle, and end of the data collection), showing the single crystal periodicity of the dataset, which is a quality indicator of the crystal tracking precision achieved, despite a few extra reflections collected from adjacent domains.

In Fig. 9 a, a picture of the 3D reconstructed reciprocal space is reported to show the extra reflections accumulated in the b^*c^* diagonal. For more details, in Fig. 3SI, the rest of the 3D reciprocal space is reported to highlight the characteristic systematic absences of the space group P2₁/n of the target monoclinic LaPO₄ phase.

From this dataset, *ab-initio* structure solution, kinematical and dynamical refinement of LaPO₄ is possible, delivering a full characterization of the crystal structure of the material as already reported in the literature. A recap of the crystal structure investigation results is given in Table 2 SI.

In Fig. 5SI the scattered / transmitted beam intensity plots are reported for all the ADT datasets acquired. From the 4 LaPO₄ datasets (2, 3, 6, 7), the I/I_{000} ratio never reaches the zero, scoring a tracking success of 4/4. 3 experiments (2, 3, 6) delivered a structure solution of the LaPO₄ phase, scoring 3/4 LaPO₄ dataset successfully solved, as reported

in Table 3 SI.

3.7. Fully automated 3D ED cRED data acquisition from very small nanocrystals

Nowadays, ADT is the standard approach to collect 3D ED data from small nanocrystals below 100 nm [17,42,43], because it is the easiest approach to combine with manual data acquisition and no automation is required. cRED presents advantages in terms of data quality, such as absence of Sg parabolic distortions from the precession method [44], around 3 times faster dynamical refinement [29], and faster data acquisition both with and without applying crystal tracking, resulting in a lower total electron fluence deposited on the sample. Nevertheless, several disadvantages, such as the lack of stage reproducibility, a high degree of automation required for both alpha tilt and detector acquisition synchronization, and an optimization of the most reproducible stage alpha tilt speeds to achieve the required precision, hinder 3D ED cRED data acquisition of these very small nanocrystals. From our previous reproducibility analysis, stepwise acquisition can reach a reasonable crystal tracking precision performance. Continuous acquisition precision is in the same ballpark, but lower precision is expected.

14 datasets are collected from glass ceramic sample, where in 7 of them, the unit cell of the target LaPO₄ is found. The best dataset (exp_14) in terms of % non-empty frames, R_{int} , completeness, is reported here. In Table 4 SI is reported the statistics up to structure solution of the collected datasets. The aim is to assess the necessary steps to enable full automation of the cRED method in a qualitative way for future

development.

A crystal tracking file using PatchworkCC is generated between -44 and +49 degrees in a continuous approach, and the obtained crystal tracking path from PatchworkCC is shown in Fig. 8 a. Again, here, the CC object detection method results in 5 wrong positions over 140 measured, scattered away from the correct crystal path from false positive peaks in the CC calculation, while the PatchworkCC algorithm automatically corrects these positions in agreement with the manual path. In Fig. 8 b, from the 3D ED cRED dataset collected the scattered / transmitted beam intensity ratio for each frame is reported.

The plot never approaches the zero line, meaning that all the diffraction patterns contain reflections and no empty frames are collected. Moreover, this plot shows that, up to frame 40, the dataset presents a negative slope for the intensity ratio, related to the presence of many weak polycrystalline reflections. From frame 40 up to the end, several spikes are found, related to an improvement in the single crystal quality of the data.

In Fig. 8 c, three cRED patterns are shown to highlight three different parts of the plot in Fig. 8 b (around start, mid, and end of the data collection) and show the trend described of the dataset, where at the beginning the dataset present many reflections from adjacent crystals, and following there is an improvement of the data quality towards the end of the dataset.

In Fig. 9 b, a picture of the 3D reconstructed reciprocal space is reported. Again, extra reflections from adjacent crystallites accumulated in the b^*c^* diagonal are found, like in the ADT case. For more details, in Fig. 4SI is reported the rest of the 3D reciprocal space and the sections

containing the characteristic systematic absences of the space group $P2_1/n$.

From this dataset, only an *ab-initio* structure solution of LaPO_4 is doable, due to its limited quality. A recap of the crystal structure investigation results is given in Table 2 SI.

In Fig. 6SI the scattered / transmitted beam intensity plots are reported for all the cRED datasets acquired. From the 7 LaPO_4 datasets, in 5 experiments (2, 4, 6, 9 and 11) the I/I_{000} ratio approaches the zero, synonymous of tracking failure. Instead, in 2 of them (5, and 14), the I/I_{000} ratio never reaches the zero, scoring a tracking success of 2/7. Nevertheless, 4 experiments (5, 6, 9, 14) delivered a structure solution of the LaPO_4 phase, scoring 4/7 LaPO_4 dataset successfully solved, as reported in Table 4 SI.

By comparing all the ADT and cRED datasets collected, in the cRED method several datasets, display clear tracking failure (8/14), as reported in Fig. 6SI. Instead, for the ADT method, no tracking failure are scored (0/7), as reported in Fig. 5SI. This result highlights the worse tracking precision performance of the continuous method, that still is in the same ballpark as the stepwise one.

4. Discussion and conclusion

Many facilities nowadays still need to use semi-automated routines or manual approach for 3D ED data collection, especially when really high precision is required to collect single crystal data from very small nanocrystals. This is largely due to the absence of universal software and hardware solutions requiring modifications to source code, creating a

Fig. 8. Crystal tracking path of LaPO_4 crystal using different object detection methods (red, blue, and yellow dots are respectively positions from CC, PatchworkCC, and manual picking) calculated from continuous rotation HAADF images. The scalebar reported is 400 nm (a). Scattered / transmitted beam intensity ratio versus frame number plot. The transmitted (000) beam intensity is computed by summing pixel counts within a circular mask around the 000 beam, while all intensity outside this mask is treated as scattered signal. Their ratio is calculated for each frame and shown as a function of frame number (b). Single crystal continuous rotation electron diffraction patterns collected from LaPO_4 . From left to right, these are frame numbers with * in plot (c).

Fig. 9. 3D reciprocal space reconstruction of LaPO_4 3D ED datasets acquired using ADT (a) and cRED (b) approaches. Extra reflections are accumulated in the $b^* c^*$ diagonal for both datasets.

barrier, especially for non-programming users. Automation is beneficial in many ways, ranging from “easy to learn” and “easy to use” to an increased accuracy, and speed of data acquisition. The PyFast-ADT framework addresses this gap by lowering the programming barrier and improving shareability within the 3D ED community. In addition, the framework delivers a basis for new dedicated automation procedures for advanced applications, especially for 3D ED, but also for methods such as cryo-EM, and 4D-STEM.

Beyond enabling data collection, PyFast-ADT also contributes to the *pre-calibration* crystal tracking method improvement and facility optimization in this direction by providing tools to characterize the goniometer behaviour, thanks to the crystal tracking precision protocol. Despite the emergence of AI-based solutions, Cross-Correlation (CC) remains the most widely used approach for object detection in electron microscopy workflows, particularly in the electron tomography field. However, CC is often unreliable due to variations in shape, contrast, or the presence of multiple crystals in the field of view; thus, manual picking is commonly used for improvement. The new method described here, PatchworkCC, combines CC with a Kalman Filter (KF), showing significantly better performance. The KF enforces physically meaningful and smooth trajectories, improving robustness without adding computational complexity. Importantly, this approach could also benefit real-space electron tomography, where CC is heavily used for image alignment in tomogram reconstruction. The comparison of manual picking crystal tracking with the fully automated one performed from PatchworkCC shows that automation not only yields better average accuracy but also reduces user bias. In the case of small particles (~ 25 nm), manual picking precision is nearly twice the particle size aimed, compromising tracking quality and, consequently, could affect the quality of the 3D ED data.

The investigation of nanocrystals is strongly tied to goniometer reproducibility in the *pre-calibration* crystal tracking method. Unlike in real space electron tomography, where post-processing can mitigate stage instabilities, 3D ED relies on diffraction data, making goniometer reproducibility essential. While backlash, O-ring aging, and mechanical wear are known sources of variability, an additional factor is found. A rapid decrease behaviour is found in tracking precision curves during successive tomographic experiments. To address it, the HiPerGonio procedure is introduced, which stabilizes performance and significantly improves reproducibility, ensuring the maximum precision is achieved from the first run. While some microscope/holder pairs reached optimal precision in their first iteration, others could require multiple iterations

to achieve stable performance. Due to this effect, it is strongly suggested to characterize it using the tools presented in PyFast-ADT. If a rapid decrease behaviour is detected, the assumption of comparability between the pre-experiment and any tomography experiment is wrong, and the use of HiPerGonio is mandatory. This effect is not limited to 3D ED but also impacts Cryo-EM works, where defocus and image shift calibration tables are used during tomography data acquisition. Because these procedures also rely on an *pre-calibration* approach, the same rapid decrease behaviour in stage reproducibility can compromise the effect of the calibration itself [31].

Another systematic comparison revealed differences between microscope/holder pairs. In the Tecnai F30, the FEI single tilt tomography holder achieved sufficient precision for investigating crystals down to 25 nm. In the Tecnai Spirit, the same holder performed even better using HiPerGonio. The Simple Origin cryo-tomography holder, being 4.5 times heavier, achieved only a precision sufficient to measure nanocrystals about 100 nm size in the Tecnai F30 and 40 nm size for the Tecnai Spirit. The two investigated holders are quite different in design and scope. The FEI single-tilt holder is light (136 g) and well balanced, while the Simple Origin cryo-tomography holder weighs ~ 634 g and has a shifted center of gravity due to the liquid nitrogen reservoir. These results underline that it is necessary for precise tomography experiments to adjust the stage for one specific holder. The second reason for the different behaviour could be the age and the maintenance status of the used instruments.

Looking forward, these experiments emphasize important considerations for the design and maintenance of electron microscopes. Integrated goniometers already present in new instruments that employ cartridge-based grids (autoloaders) may provide stable and reproducible performance after tomographic optimization, especially for cryogenic applications. This improvement arises from eliminating the liquid nitrogen reservoir at the extremity of the stage. For traditional external cryo-holders, close collaboration with instrument engineers will be crucial to improve mechanical alignment and minimize variability, since these holders remain essential tools when autoloaders are not available.

In terms of the best choice of TEM, additional demands need to be taken into account. While the Tecnai Spirit consistently delivered better tracking precision than the Tecnai F30, practical limitations ultimately disqualified it for 25 nm nanocrystal measurements. First, compared to the Spirit’s LaB_6 gun, the Tecnai F30 Field Emission Gun provides a more coherent and smaller probe size, allowing for a beam of 25 nm with 0.4 mrad convergence. Second, mechanical characteristics resulted in

larger crystal shifts ($\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$) for the Spirit and during tilting compared to approximately 600 nm in the Tecnai F30.

Third, the reduced electron fluence for imaging is negligible in STEM mode [45]. This feature makes the Tecnai F30 a more suitable choice for very small nanocrystal studies, that are sensible materials to electron beam damage [46]. In addition, STEM provides practical automation advantages, such as in-place calibration of beam shift, robust HAADF imaging for tracking, and easier control of probe positioning. These factors reduce operator intervention, condenser and projector lens hysteresis, and errors connected to the pre-calibration crystal tracking method, making STEM our preferred mode for low-dimensional materials [10,45].

Finally, we demonstrated that PyFast-ADT enables automated measurement of highly challenging samples, such as LaPO_4 nanocrystals of 25 nm embedded in an amorphous/crystalline matrix. While achieving sub-25 nm precision is currently limited by mechanics, the method sets a benchmark for routine, reproducible, and automated 3D ED. Comparisons with cRED showed that, although ADT yielded superior precision in this context, cRED remains a valuable complementary approach for larger crystals. However, reproducible evaluation of tracking precision in cRED is complicated by fluctuation in goniometer speed and acquisition timing, underscoring the need for further method development in this direction.

In conclusion, our work demonstrates that robust automation, characterization of microscope/holder performance, and targeted optimization of experimental setups are crucial for extending 3D ED to the smallest nanocrystals. The workflows introduced here, particularly PatchworkCC and HiPerGonio, offer practical solutions that can be readily implemented in existing facilities, advancing the field toward fully automated nanocrystal structure determination.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

After the initial draft was finished by the author, ChatGPT was used as an editorial tool to improve the language and readability of the manuscript. The LLM tool was asked to suggest possible improvements on writing for each paragraph and find grammar errors. The LLM tool was only applied to the text and not to the figures, tables.

Code availability

PyFast-ADT is hosted on a GitHub repository, and its documentation is available on ReadTheDocs.

GitHub: <https://github.com/MSantucci/PyFast-ADT>

ReadTheDocs: <https://pyfast-adt.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marco Santucci: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Data curation. **Ute Kolb:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Marco Santucci reports financial support was provided by the European Union's H2020, grant agreement No. 956099 (NanED–Electron Nanocrystallography–H2020-MSCA-ITN). Ute Kolb reports a relationship with Eldico Company that includes: board membership. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

The data is uploaded to [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org), the program code is available on [GitHub](https://github.com), the software documentation is provided on [ReadTheDocs](https://readthedocs.org). All references are attached.

References

- [1] P. Simoncic, E. Romeijn, E. Hovestreydt, G. Steinfeld, G. Santiso-Quiñones, J. Merkelbach, Electron crystallography and dedicated electron-diffraction instrumentation, *Acta Cryst. E* 79 (5) (2023) 410–422, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2056989023003109>. Apr.
- [2] T. Gruene, E. Mugnaioli, 3D electron diffraction for chemical analysis: instrumentation developments and innovative applications, *Chem. Rev.* 121 (19) (2021) 11823–11834, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.1c00207>. Oct.
- [3] V. Hutskalova, C. Jandl, A. Prescimone, C. Sparr, Determination of the absolute configuration by 3D ED to elucidate the atroposelectivity in aromatic ring-opening metathesis, *Chimia* 79 (2025) 255–258, <https://doi.org/10.2533/chimia.2025.255>. Apr.
- [4] K.-N. Truong, et al., Making the most of 3D electron diffraction: best practices to handle a new tool, *Symmetry* 15 (8) (2023) 1555, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym15081555>. Aug.
- [5] M.A. Hegazy, A.M. Abd El-Hameed, Characterization of CdSe-nanocrystals used in semiconductors for aerospace applications: Production and optical properties, *NRIAG J. Astron. Geophys.* 3 (1) (2014) 82–87, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nrjag.2014.05.002>. Jun.
- [6] S. Murthy, P. Effiong, C.C. Fei, 11 - Metal oxide nanoparticles in biomedical applications, in: Y. Al-Douri (Ed.), *Metal Oxide Powder Technologies*, Elsevier, 2020, pp. 233–251, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817505-7.00011-7>. Metal Oxides.
- [7] A. Tarafder, A.R. Molla, B. Karmakar, Chapter 13 - Advanced Glass-Ceramic Nanocomposites for Structural, Photonic, and Optoelectronic Applications, in: B. Karmakar, K. Rademann, A.L. Stepanov (Eds.), *Glass Nanocomposites*, William Andrew Publishing, Boston, 2016, pp. 299–338, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-39309-6.00013-4>.
- [8] V. Nagal, et al., Chapter 25 - Metal halide perovskite nanomaterials for battery applications, in: A. Khan, M. Nazim, A. Asiri (Eds.), *Advances in Electronic Materials for Clean Energy Conversion and Storage Applications*, Woodhead Publishing Series in Electronic and Optical Materials, Woodhead Publishing, 2023, pp. 537–568, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-91206-8.00024-8>.
- [9] B. Wang, X. Zou, S. Smeets, Automated serial rotation electron diffraction combined with cluster analysis: an efficient multi-crystal workflow for structure determination, *IUCrJ* 6 (5) (2019) 854–867, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2052252519007681>. Sep.
- [10] S. Plana-Ruiz, et al., Fast-ADT: A fast and automated electron diffraction tomography setup for structure determination and refinement, *Ultramicroscopy* 211 (2020) 112951, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2020.112951>. Apr.
- [11] M.J. de la Cruz, M.W. Martynowicz, J. Hattne, T. Gonen, MicroED data collection with SerialEM, *Ultramicroscopy* 201 (2019) 77–80, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2019.03.009>. Jun.
- [12] Klementova, M. & Palatinus, L., *RATS, software for collection of 3D ED data*. Institute of Physics of the CAS, Prague, Czechia.
- [13] D.N. Mastrorade, SerialEM: A program for automated tilt series acquisition on tecnai microscopes using prediction of specimen position, *Microanal* 9 (S02) (2003) 1182–1183, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927603445911>. Aug.
- [14] C. Suloway, et al., Automated molecular microscopy: The new Legimon system, *J. Struct. Biol.* 151 (1) (2005) 41–60, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsb.2005.03.010>. Jul.
- [15] S. Passuti, J. Varignon, A. David, P. Boullay, Scanning precession electron tomography (SPET) for structural analysis of thin films along their thickness, *Symmetry* 15 (7) (2023) 1459, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym15071459>. Jul.
- [16] M. Gallagher-Jones, et al., Atomic structures determined from digitally defined nanocrystalline regions, *IUCrJ* 7 (3) (2020) 490–499, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2052252520004030>. May.
- [17] E. Mugnaioli, T. Gorelik, U. Kolb, Ab initio structure solution from electron diffraction data obtained by a combination of automated diffraction tomography and precession technique, *Ultramicroscopy* 109 (6) (2009) 758–765, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2009.01.011>. May.

- [18] J. Liu, et al., Fully mechanically controlled automated electron microscopic tomography, *Sci. Rep.* 6 (1) (2016) 29231, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep29231>. Jul.
- [19] P. Gollé-Leidreiter, B. Durschang, U. Kolb, G. SEXTL, Crystal structure determination of a new LaPO₄ phase in a multicomponent glass ceramic via 3D electron diffraction, *Ceram. Int.* 48 (3) (2022) 3790–3799, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2021.10.162>. Feb.
- [20] I. Nederlof, E. van Genderen, Y.-W. Li, J.P. Abrahams, A Medipix quantum area detector allows rotation electron diffraction data collection from submicrometre three-dimensional protein crystals, *Acta Cryst. D* 69 (7) (2013) 1223–1230, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0907444913009700>. Jul.
- [21] B.L. Nannenga, D. Shi, A.G.W. Leslie, T. Gonen, High-resolution structure determination by continuous-rotation data collection in MicroED, *Nat. Methods* 11 (9) (2014) 927–930, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.3043>. Sep.
- [22] M. Gemmi, M.G.I. La Placa, A.S. Galanis, E.F. Rauch, S. Nicolopoulos, Fast electron diffraction tomography, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 48 (3) (2015) 718–727, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576715004604>. Jun.
- [23] Y. Wang, et al., Elucidation of the elusive structure and formula of the active pharmaceutical ingredient bismuth subgallate by continuous rotation electron diffraction, *Chem. Commun.* 53 (52) (2017) 7018–7021, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7CC03180G>. Jun.
- [24] U. Kolb, E. Mugnaioli, T.E. Gorelik, Automated electron diffraction tomography – a new tool for nano crystal structure analysis, *Cryst. Res. Technol.* 46 (6) (2011) 542–554, <https://doi.org/10.1002/crat.201100036>.
- [25] L. Palatinus, P. Brázda, M. Jelínek, J. Hrdá, G. Steciuk, M. Klementová, Specifics of the data processing of precession electron diffraction tomography data and their implementation in the program PETS2.0, *Acta Cryst. B* 75 (4) (2019) 512–522, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2052520619007534>. Aug.
- [26] M.C. Burla, et al., Crystal structure determination and refinement via SIR2014, *J. Appl. Cryst.* 48 (1) (2015) 306–309, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576715001132>. Feb.
- [27] V. Petříček, L. Palatinus, J. Plášil, M. Dušek, Jana2020 – a new version of the crystallographic computing system Jana, *Z. Krist. - Cryst. Mater.* 238 (7–8) (2023) 271–282, <https://doi.org/10.1515/zkri-2023-0005>. Jul.
- [28] L. Palatinus, V. Petříček, C.A. Corrêa, Structure refinement using precession electron diffraction tomography and dynamical diffraction: theory and implementation, *Acta Cryst. A* 71 (2) (2015) 235–244, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2053273315001266>. Mar.
- [29] P.B. Klar, et al., Accurate structure models and absolute configuration determination using dynamical effects in continuous-rotation 3D electron diffraction data, *Nat. Chem.* 15 (6) (2023) 848–855, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41557-023-01186-1>. Jun.
- [30] U. Ziese, et al., Automated high-throughput electron tomography by pre-calibration of image shifts, *J. Microsc.* 205 (2) (2002) 187–200, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0022-2720.2001.00987.x>.
- [31] D.N. Mastronarde, Automated electron microscope tomography using robust prediction of specimen movements, *J. Struct. Biol.* 152 (1) (2005) 36–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsb.2005.07.007>. Oct.
- [32] Q.S. Zheng, M.B. Braunfeld, J.W. Sedat, D.A. Agard, An improved strategy for automated electron microscopic tomography, *J. Struct. Biol.* 147 (2) (2004) 91–101, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsb.2004.02.005>. Aug.
- [33] R.E. Kalman, A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems, *J. Basic Eng.* 82 (1) (1960) 35–45, <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3662552>. Mar.
- [34] G. Welch and G. Bishop, “Welch & bishop, an introduction to the Kalman filter 2 1 the discrete Kalman filter in 1960,” presented at the International Conference on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques, 1994.
- [35] Y. Kim and H. Bang, “Introduction to Kalman filter and its applications,” 2018. doi: 10.5772/intechopen.80600.
- [36] R. Sainju, et al., DefectTrack: a deep learning-based multi-object tracking algorithm for quantitative defect analysis of in-situ TEM videos in real-time, *Sci. Rep.* 12 (1) (2022) 15705, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-19697-1>. Sep.
- [37] Y. Qian, J.Z. Huang, C. Park, Y. Ding, Fast dynamic nonparametric distribution tracking in electron microscopic data, *Ann. Appl. Stat.* 13 (3) (2019) 1537–1563, <https://doi.org/10.1214/19-AOAS1245>. Sep.
- [38] S. Bogatin, K. Foppe, P. Wasmeier, T.A. Wunderlich, T. Schäfer, D. Kogoj, Evaluation of linear Kalman filter processing geodetic kinematic measurements, *Measurement* 41 (5) (2008) 561–578, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2007.03.003>. Jun.
- [39] A. Ahmed, “OBJECT DETECTION AND TRACKING USING KALMAN FILTER AND FAST MEAN SHIFT ALGORITHM,” presented at the International Conference on Computer Vision Theory and Applications, Dec. 2025, pp. 585–589.
- [40] D. Lopanov, *LdDI/kalman-filter*. Dec. 13, 2025. <https://github.com/LdDI/kalman-filter>.
- [41] FilterPy — FilterPy 1.4.4 documentation. <https://filterpy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.
- [42] A. Lanza, E. Margheritis, E. Mugnaioli, V. Cappello, G. Garau, M. Gemmi, Nanobeam precession-assisted 3D electron diffraction reveals a new polymorph of hen egg-white lysozyme, *IUCrJ.* 6 (2019) 178–188, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2052252518017657>. Pt 2Jan.
- [43] E. Mugnaioli, M. Gemmi, Single-crystal analysis of nanodomains by electron diffraction tomography: mineralogy at the order-disorder borderline, *Z. Krist. - Cryst. Mater.* 233 (3–4) (2018) 163–178, <https://doi.org/10.1515/zkri-2017-2130>. Mar.
- [44] P. Brázda, M. Klementová, Y. Krysiak, L. Palatinus, Accurate lattice parameters from 3D electron diffraction data. I. Optical distortions, *IUCrJ.* 9 (6) (2022) 735–755, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2052252522007904>. Nov.
- [45] U. Kolb, T. Gorelik, C. Kübel, M.T. Otten, D. Hubert, Towards automated diffraction tomography: part I—Data acquisition, *Ultramicroscopy* 107 (6) (2007) 507–513, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2006.10.007>. Jun.
- [46] E.Cordero Oyonarte, et al., 3D electron diffraction on nanoparticles: minimal size and associated dynamical effects, *ACS. Nano* 19 (22) (2025) 20599–20612, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.5c01764>. Jun.